

Supporting Information

Halogen Bond-Driven Reversible Thermochromism in a Two-Dimensional Hybrid Perovskite

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Figure S1. ConQuest (CCDC software) search scheme for deposited single crystal structures displaying halogen-halogen contacts between organic halides and metal halides. *No deposited single crystal structures based on Ge have been found.

The above criteria (**Figure S1**) return 233 results: 14 results of 1D metal (13 for Pb, 1 for Sn, 0 for Ge) halide chains, 18 results of quasi-3D multilayered metal (16 for Pb, 2 for Sn, 0 for Ge) halides, 42 results for 2D metal halides and the remaining 159 results refer to irrelevant metal salts. Utilizing the Mercury software (CCDC software) we observe actual halogen-halogen contacts between organic halides and metal halides in 10 out of 13 1D structures, in 13 out of 18 quasi-3D multilayered structures and in 15 out of 42 2D metal halide structures. In 2D metal halides the most common halogen-halogen contact, is the iodine-iodine contact which emerges when alkylammonium iodides and metal iodides are utilized (I-I in 9 out of 15 results, Br-Br in 3 out of 15, F-Br in 2 out of 15, Br-I in 1 out of 15). The utilized alkylammonium cations and metal iodides are summarized in the following Table showing the chemical structures of the utilized alkylammonium iodides and the CCDC identifier of the deposited single crystal structures of the 2D metal halides.

Table S1. Summary of the deposited single crystal structures of 2D metal halides having iodine-iodine contacts. Chemical structures of the utilized alkylammonium iodides and the CCDC identifier of the deposited single crystal structures of the 2D metal halides are also displayed.

2D layered lead (II) iodides									
Entry	CCDC Identifier	Ions	Space Group	Layer Shift*	Entry	CCDC Identifier	Ions	Space Group	Layer Shift*
1	TEYMIU, TEYMIU01, TEYMIU02, TEYMIU03	 PbI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	nDJ	2	NUXHIY, NUXHIY01, NUXHIY02	 H ₃ N ⁺ , PbI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	nRP
3	SIFSEJ, SIFSEJ01, SIFSEJ02	 , PbI ₄ ⁻	Aba2	RP	4	SIFSOT, SIFSOT01,	 , PbI ₄ ⁻	Aba2	RP
5	NUXHOE	 H ₃ N ⁺ , PbI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	nDJ	6	LOLNEJ	 PbI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	nDJ
7	NUXHUK	 H ₃ N ⁺ , PbI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	DJ	8	NUXJAS, NUXJAS01	 , PbI ₄ ⁻	Pbca	RP
2D layered tin (II) iodides									
9	TEGROQ	 SnI ₄ ⁻	P2 ₁ /c	nDJ					

* nDJ (“near Dion-Jacobson”) and nRP (“near Ruddlesden-Popper”) assignments refer to structures approaching the ideal cases.

Table S2. Calculated main geometrical parameters and energetic stability difference for the isolated 2-X-ethylammonium (X= Cl, Br, I) cations in the anti- and syn- conformation.

X	conformer	d_{C-X} (Å)	d_{H-X} (Å)	dihedron _{X-C-C-N} (°)	$E_{syn}-E_{anti}$ (kcal/mol)
Cl	Anti	1.788	/	180.0	0
Cl	Syn	1.805	2.509	55.5	-1.41
Br	Anti	1.953	/	180.0	0
Br	Syn	1.971	2.526	54.7	-1.39
I	Anti	2.187	/	180.0	0
I	Syn	2.202	2.781	57.9	0.01

Figure S2. Optimized geometry for the 2EIA⁺ cation (left); Molecular electrostatic potential related to the entire cation (middle) and focusing on the halogen atom (right, energy scale in kcal/mol).

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum of the 2IEA-I salt recorded in D_2O .

Figure S4. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the 2IEA-I salt recorded in D_2O .

Figure S5. ESI-MS spectrum of the 2IEA-I salt.

Figure S6. FT-IR spectrum of the 2IEA-I salt highlighting the C-I bond stretching band.

Figure S7. Thermogravimetric analysis of the 2IEA-I salt.

Table S3. Crystallographic data for the 2IEA-I salt at 200K.

Chemical formula	C ₂ H ₇ I ₂ N
Molecular weight	298.89
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, P2 ₁ /c
Temperature (K)	200.00(10)
a, b, c (Å)	8.3370(4), 8.8875(5), 9.4514(5)
α, β, γ (°)	90, 102.096(5), 90
V (Å³)	684.75(6)
Z	4
ρ_{calc}/cm³	2.899
μ/mm⁻¹	71.125
F(000)	528.0
Crystal size/mm³	0.196 × 0.127 × 0.06
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	10.854 to 152.44
Index ranges	-9 ≤ h ≤ 10, -9 ≤ k ≤ 10, -10 ≤ l ≤ 11
Reflections collected	3928
Independent reflections	1295 [R _{int} = 0.0903, R _{sigma} = 0.0704]
Data/restraints/parameters	1295/0/48
Goodness-of-fit on F²	1.151
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0593, wR ₂ = 0.1686
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0641, wR ₂ = 0.1736
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å⁻³	2.41/-2.49

Electron density difference map (2F₀-F_c)

CCDC Number

2477300

Figure S8. X-ray diffraction spectra of the 2IEA-I salt.

Figure S9. Conformation of 2IEA⁺ at a) 200K and b) 300K, as found in the asymmetric unit observed from SCXRD analysis.

Table S4. Crystallographic data for the 2IEA-I salt at 300K.

Chemical formula	C ₂ H ₇ I ₂ N
Molecular weight	298.89
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, P2 ₁ /c
Temperature (K)	297.50(10)
a, b, c (Å)	8.3705(2), 8.9215(2), 9.5434(2)
α, β, γ (°)	90, 102.171(2), 90
V (Å³)	696.66(3)
Z	4
ρ_{calc} g/cm³	2.850
μ/mm⁻¹	69.909
F(000)	528.0
Crystal size/mm³	0.122x0.089x0.046
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	0.812 to 153.248
Index ranges	-9 ≤ h ≤ 10, -10 ≤ k ≤ 7, -10 ≤ l ≤ 11
Reflections collected	4356
Independent reflections	1347 [R _{int} = 0.0531, R _{sigma} = 0.0480]
Data/restraints/parameters	1347/0/47
Goodness-of-fit on F²	1.085
Final R indexes [I >= 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0522, wR ₂ = 0.1371
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0570, wR ₂ = 0.1411
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å⁻³	1.53/-1.80

ORTEP diagram: 19-488

CCDC number

2477301

Figure S10. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and the first derivative of weight loss in respect to temperature (Deriv. Weight) for the $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$.

Figure S11. Variable-temperature ^{13}C CP-MAS NMR spectra of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ performed with a contact time of 2 ms and a spinning speed of 8 kHz.

Figure S12. Illustration of the position of the 2IEA^+ cation within the inorganic slabs of Phase 1 (300K) $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals, as evidenced by single crystal X-ray diffraction.

Table S5. Crystallographic data for the Phase 2 of the $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ at 360K.

Chemical formula	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{NI})_2\text{PbI}_4$
Molecular weight	1058.80
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, $P2_1/c$
Temperature (K)	359.99(10)
a, b, c (Å)	8.6572(5), 8.8383(4), 26.1874(15)
α, β, γ (°)	90, 99.021(5), 90
V (Å³)	1978.94(19)
Z	8
ρ_{calc} g/cm³	3.506
μ/mm⁻¹	89.887
F(000)	1752.0
Crystal size/mm³	0.17 × 0.06 × 0.03
Radiation	Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.836 to 82.49
Index ranges	$-7 \leq h \leq 7, -7 \leq k \leq 7, -21 \leq l \leq 22$
Reflections collected	6754
Independent reflections	1271 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0988, R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0435$]
Data/restraints/parameters	1271/0/94
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.121
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0771, wR_2 = 0.2183$
Final R indexes [all data]	$R_1 = 0.0813, wR_2 = 0.2220$
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å⁻³	2.99/-2.01

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Electron density difference map ($2F_0 - F_c$)

CCDC Number

2477302

Figure S13. Illustration of the position of the discrete alternating anti- and syn-conformers of the 2IEA^+ cation within the inorganic slabs of the new $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystalline phase, Phase 2 (360K) as evidenced by single crystal X-ray diffraction.

Figure S14. Rietveld refinement for $(2IEA)_2PbI_4$ at 300K (Phase 1) and 360K (Phase 2).

Figure S15. Variable temperature X-ray diffraction for $(2IEA)_2PbI_4$ at reflection geometry.

Figure S16. Left: Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) graphs of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals for the 1st, 45th and 75th heating run. Right: XRD patterns for the as-prepared $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals (top) and after the 45th (middle) and the 75th (bottom) DSC thermal cycling.

Figure S17. Variable temperature X-ray diffraction for $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals at reflection geometry. Heating cycle of $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, 2min equilibration before each measurement.

Figure S18. Variable temperature X-ray diffraction for (2IEA)₂PbI₄ crystals at reflection geometry. Cooling cycle of 2°C/min, 2min equilibration before each measurement.

Figure S19. Band structure of a) Phase 1 (blue) and b) Phase 2 (red) $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ perovskite (PBE-SOC level); the zero energy is set in both cases at the highest occupied state.

Figure S20. Band structure for selected direction around Γ of Phase 1 (blue), a) and b), and Phase 2 (red), c) and d), $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ perovskite (PBE-SOC level); the zero energy is set in all cases at the highest occupied state.

Figure S21. Projected density of states (PDOS) of a) Phase 1 and b) Phase 2 $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ perovskite (HSE-SOC level); the zero energy is set in both cases at the highest occupied state.

Table S6. Calculated effective masses in units of the free electron $0.1m_0$ for the Phase 1 and Phase 2 $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ structures (PBE-SOC level).

	electron		Hole	
	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 1	Phase 2
$\Gamma\text{-B}$	0.11	0.11	0.21	0.20
$\Gamma\text{-Z}$	0.11	0.11	0.19	0.17
$\Gamma\text{-A}$	0.14	0.10	0.26	0.20
$\Gamma\text{-E}$	0.14	0.11	0.25	0.19
$\Gamma\text{-M}$	0.12	0.11	0.21	0.20
$\Gamma\text{-Y2}$	∞	∞	∞	∞

Figure S22. Absorbance, PL emission (exc. 400nm) and PL excitation (emi. 740nm) of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals at room temperature. The absorbance region of 550-800nm is 4-time magnified.

Figure S23. PL emission (exc.400nm) of $(2IEA)_2PbI_4$ crystals at 200K and 300K.

Figure S24. Time-resolved PL spectra for the main three peaks: a) at 496nm (exc. 445nm); b) at 535nm (exc. 445nm) and c) at 720nm (exc.480nm); of $2IEA_2PbI_4$ crystals at room temperature.

Figure S25. PL emission of an individual $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystal (confocal microscope, exc. 405 nm) and bulk PL emission (exc. 400nm) of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals and powder samples at room temperature.

Figure S26. Confocal PL emission spectra of an individual $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystal in a heating-cooling cycle.

Table S7. Stability of Unit Cell Parameters over Time for $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$

	November 2023	March 2024	March 2026
a (Å)	12.7329(4)	12.7217(2)	12.7248(8)
b (Å)	8.7282(3)	8.7261(2)	8.7280(6)
c (Å)	8.7462(3)	8.7408(2)	8.7358(5)
α (°)	90	90	90
β (°)	97.712(3)	97.715(2)	97.774(7)
γ (°)	90	90	90
V (Å ³)	963.22(6)	961.54(4)	961.30(11)

This table reports the crystallographic unit cell parameters collected at different time points (November 2023, March 2024, and March 2026) on the same batch stored under ambient conditions. The negligible variations observed for lattice parameters and unit cell volume confirm the long-term structural stability of the material over more than two years. These results support the absence of degradation or phase evolution.

November 2023 (light green) vs March 2026 (colour code as Fig S13) with RMSD = 0.0035

March 2024 (light blue) vs March 2026 (colour code as Fig S13) with RMSD = 0.0019

Figure S27. Structural Overlay Demonstrating Long-Term Stability (November 2023 vs March 2026, left) and (March 2024 vs March 2026, right)

The superposition of the single-crystal structures collected in November 2023 and March 2026 (left) and March 2024 and March 2026 (right) shows an excellent agreement, with an RMSD of 0.0035 Å and 0.0019 Å, respectively. This near-perfect overlap demonstrates that the crystal structure is preserved over time without detectable structural rearrangements. The result provides strong evidence of the intrinsic robustness of the material under prolonged storage conditions.

Figure S28. PXRD comparison of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ collected in November 2023 and March 2026

The PXRD patterns collected in November 2023 (black) and March 2026 (red) show a high degree of similarity, with all diffraction peaks appearing at the same 2θ positions. This indicates that the crystal structure is preserved over time, with no evidence of phase transformation or degradation after prolonged storage under ambient conditions. The absence of peak shifts confirms that the lattice parameters remain essentially unchanged, while the lack of new reflections excludes the formation of secondary phases or decomposition products.

Overall, the excellent agreement between the two patterns demonstrates the long-term structural stability of the material, supporting the claim that $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ maintains its crystallographic integrity over extended periods.

Table S8. Temperature-dependent Photoluminescence Quantum Yields (Φ) of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals

	Temperature (K)	Φ (%)
Phase 1	248	1.2
Phase 1	298	0.9
Phase 2	353	0.7

Figure S29. DSC curves of $(2\text{IEA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ crystals: as-prepared (solid line) vs. 30-months aged (dotted line) samples

